

Eclipse Essentials: Safe and Stylish Solar Viewing Glasses

Steps:

1. Decorate the pre-cut template.
2. Slide the earpieces into each slit, taking care not to damage the lenses.
3. Prevent light from seeping in by taping the top of the glasses to the plate and on the inside of the plate.
4. Observe the Sun safely and stylishly anytime!

Credit: My NASA Data

Slide the earpieces into the slits.

Tape the top of the glasses to the inside of the mask.

 Explore the Full Activity:
science.nasa.gov/learn/heat/resource/eclipse-essentials-safe-and-stylish-solar-eclipse-glasses/

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Talking Points

- **Are you ready for the total solar eclipse tomorrow (today)?**
 - Do you have the tools you need to be safe?
 - Solar Viewing glasses are one tool you can use to safely view the Sun.
 - You can use these glasses to view the Sun anytime, but they are especially useful for viewing a partial solar eclipse.
- **Tomorrow's eclipse will start as a partial eclipse and then become a total solar eclipse.**
 - The partial eclipse begins at _____ as the Moon's shadow starts to obscure part of the Sun.
 - Slowly, the Sun will become more and more obscured, until the Sun is 100% blocked at _____.
 - At that point, you can take off your solar viewing glasses for about 4 minutes during totality. This is the only time it is safe to look directly at the Sun without special equipment. The Moon's shadow is blocking the light that would otherwise damage your eyes.
 - You will have to put your glasses back on at _____, when the Moon's shadow starts to move away from the Sun.
 - You can continue to watch the partial solar eclipse until _____, when the shadow moves completely off of the Sun.
- **During totality you will be able to see the Sun's outer atmosphere, the corona. We usually can't see the corona because it is much dimmer than the bright surface of the Sun.**
 - Scientists take this opportunity to make observations of the corona and learn more about how the Sun affects Earth.
- **Save your solar eclipse glasses and use them anytime to make observations of the Sun!**
 - Store them in a safe place and make sure there are no holes or scratches on the lenses.

